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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**A Case Report****HYPERLIPIDEMIA IN YOUNG AGE: CASE REPORT**¹ Asif Raza Gill, ² Muhammad Afzal, ³ Ms. Hajra Sarwar¹ Post RN (BSN) 2nd Semester Student, Lahore School of Nursing² Head of Department Lahore of School of Nursing³ Lecturer at Lahore School of Nursing**Article Received:** March 2019**Accepted:** April 2019**Published:** May 2019

Abstract: *The purpose of this study was to determine the prevalence of hyperlipidemia in a population. Hyperlipidemia is a noteworthy risk factor for cardiovascular disarranges. Cardiovascular disarranges or disorders are the main source of death in Pakistan. TVD (Tripplevessels disease) because of hyperlipidemia is extremely uncommon in young age. Conclusion: TVD (Tripplevessels disease) because of hyperlipidemia is extremely uncommon in young age.*

Hyperlipidemia along with a number of other risk factors, some known others unknown predisposes to Coronary Artery Disease (CAD) and its dreaded complications. The pose of this study was to determine the prevalence of hyperlipidemia in a population. Hyperlipidemia is a noteworthy hazard factor for cardiovascular disarranges. Cardiovascular disarranges or disorders are the main source of death in Pakistan. Hyperlipidemia has high mortality and horribly in light of the fact that it is the significant risk factor for developing stroke and cardiovascular issue. TVD (Tripplevessels disease) because of hyperlipidemia is extremely uncommon in young age. This study expects to give mindfulness about hyperlipidemia just as a refreshed information about the study of disease transmission and risk factor of hyperlipidemia. Adults with prolonged exposure to even moderate elevations in non-high-density lipoprotein cholesterol have elevated risk for future CHD.

Background: *Hyperlipidemia is a potent risk factor for coronary heart disease (CHD) and is present in a substantial proportion of young adults. Many young adults with hyperlipidemia do not meet statin treatment criteria under the new AHA/ACC cholesterol guidelines as they focus on 10 to 12-year cardiovascular risk. We evaluated the association between years of exposure to hypercholesterolemia in early adulthood and future coronary heart disease (CHD) risk.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Hyperlipidemia, characterized as unusually expanded levels of blood lipids or lipoproteins (most normally low-thickness lipoprotein - cholesterol, is an entrenched risk factor for atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD). Hyperlipidemia refers to raised cholesterol, raised triglycerides or both. It is a solid risk factor for CVD. Hyperlipidemia is to high level of cholesterol, or LDL, present in blood. It means there is a lot of of cholesterol in the blood. Cholesterol transforms into an issue when an abundance of cholesterol, or low-thickness lipoprotein (LDL), is made or ingested through unfortunate foods. Lipoproteins transport to cholesterol through blood to the cells. Although hyperlipidemia does not cause indications, it can altogether expand your danger of creating cardiovascular sickness, including malady of veins providing the heart (coronary supply route ailment), cerebrum (cerebrovascular ailment), and appendages (fringe vascular infection). These conditions can thus prompt chest torment, heart assaults, strokes, and different issues [08,11]

A few types of hyperlipidemia effectsly affect the body. They are sorted by the diverse kinds of fat influenced and how they impacts the body, essential or primary and auxiliary or secendory hyperlipidemia subtypes, hyperlipidemia likewise ordered by the sort of lipid raised which is hypercholesterolemia, hypertriglyceridemia or both in combined hyperlipidemia.

It might be happen, for example, use of alcohol, use of excessive medication, obesity for example, hormones or steroids, kidney malady or disease, hypothyroidism or an underactive thyroid organ, and amilial hyperlipidemia originates from a hereditary disorder. Hyperlipidemia is a typical medical issue that can lead genuine cardiovascular or coronary illness, yet it very well may be avoided and treated through the suitable medicine use and support of a heart-healthy way of life .Hyperlipidemia essentially is a confusion in which there are strangely raised dimensions of fat particles, it tends to be brought about by primary (hereditary inclination) or optional(secendory) causes (diet, underlying sickness or meds). Essential hyperlipidemia is related with high mortality and morbidity[01,12]

Hyperlipidemia is generally identified amid a normal blood test, and to following cardiovascular test, for example, stroke or heart assault. Excessive fat gathers in the blood after some passage of time, and forming plaques on dividers of supply routes and supply veins.

Self-administration is also way decrease dimensions of lipoproteins in blood. However, at times, self-overseeing hyperlipidemia may not be successful. Hyperlipidemia screened utilizing a blood test called a lipid profile. Screening may begin at 20 years old years. In the event that the outcome is ordinary, it ought to be rehashed no less than at regular intervals [06-09]

The real treatment utilized for hyperlipidemia separated into three sections which are Dietary control: This point center around diminishing admission of sustenances that contain high measure of immersed fat and cholesterol i.e., nourishments of creature inception. Then again point to will support admission of nourishment and enhancements that incorporate olive oil or fish oil which incorporate low centralization of immersed fat. And on the other hand concentrating on admission of veggie lover nourishments which are free of cholesterol. These kinds of sustenance will noteworthy assume job in lessening raised triglyceride levels. Lifestyle change: This will incorporate concentrating on every day works out, since customary activities will prompt an improvement inside lipid focuses i.e., day by day strolling will decrease triglyceride level by a normal of 10 mg/dL and height inside HDL level 5 mg/dL. • Medical medications: These medicines will be demonstrated for those patients who experience the ill effects of hyperlipidemia early youth such as familial hyperlipidemia. And these prescriptions include. HMG CoA reductase inhibitors (first line medication (treatment) for raised levels of LDL), Fibrates (also 1st line treatment of triglyceride rise), bile corrosive sequestrants (2nd line treatment for raised levels of LDL), Nicotinic corrosive (2nd line treatment for lipid issue) and Ezetimibe and colesevelam (second line medications through gastro intestinal track to lessen retention of cholesterol [07,05]

Clinical diagnosis of HLP is made primarily by a fasting lipid profile, which requires fasting for about 12 hours prior to the test. The lipid profile measures total cholesterol, triglycerides and HDL, from the, a calculated LDL can be obtained. May be LDL measured but the value is sometimes underestimated.

CASE PRESENTATION:

A 20 year old female admitted in private hospital presented with shortness of breath and chest heaviness, patient feeling difficulty in breathing during activity. Her vital sign was temp 37C, pulse

88/m, BP 110/70mm/GH and sats 92% on room air. On admission day patient told that she feel difficulty in breathing and chest pain when walk and peripheries got sinoused. Then done patient ECG, ECG is normal and cardia profile is normal according to ECG interpitations. Assess the patient completely no any abnormality seen such as pedal enema, advintious sound fint through auscultation. On physically examination patient have fat deposit patches on whole body, it is very surprising and very different finding which don't appear commonly in young age, and this very rare case according to doctor, then take patient past and family history, patient having familial hypercholesterolemia in her family history. Patient father and her two brothers are cardia patient, Patient is under treatment of CCU doctor and according to his order send patients investigations labs, patient labs are normal except LDL and cholesterol level, LDL 572, AND TOTAL LIPIDS 639 which are abnormal. An ordinary lipid profile comprises of the accompanying levels. Total cholesterol: under 200,LDL: under 100,HDL: more noteworthy than 40 for male, more prominent than 50 for females (higher is surprisingly better).ECHO done and according to echo report there are normal heart values working well , then patient angiography done and findings of angiography are patient have triple vessels disease. It is very shocking for all medical team because it is very rare in young age. Sift the patient in cadiacicu and treatment start under the supervision of all medial staff team.

Diagnose:

Tripplevessels disease due to Hyperlipidemia. The reasons for hyperlipidemia can be because of Genetic components: This is known as essential hyperlipidemia. What's more, Poor eating routine and different components: This is known as optional hyperlipidemia. Familial hyperlipidemia is a demoinantly genetic problem caused by over production athergenicapolipoprotein B containing lipoprotein it result in increase of cholesterol and TG or both in differ members of family at different time, also It is linkation with increase risk of cardiovascular disorder or disease. but it does not show pathognomonic physical sign. During operation (CABG) LIMA,RIMA Calcified not harvested,vein grafted for by pass. Tablet ascard 75mg one per day, Tablet noclot 75mg one per day, tablet lipdin 20mg one at bed time, tablet norvasc 5mg one per day, capsule omega 20mg one per day. Provide nursing care include physical activity, change life style, Normal exercise and action helps lower LDL, raise HDL, and energize weight reduction. Psycheeducational nursing intercession done to

advance self adequacy desires for walking in recvery and it is related with increasingly self revealed strolling conduct after cardiovascular medical procedure.

DISCUSSION:

Hyperlipidemia is a genetic disorder resulting in the accumulation of remnant particles stemming from a defective Apo E, resulting in an elevated cholesterol and triglyceride level. The disease is caused by defective forms of Apo E that ineffectively bind to lipoprotein receptors, leading to accumulation of chylomicron and VLDL remnants. Common precipitants of hypertriglyceridemia include type 2 diabetes, hypothyroidism, renal failure, obesity, alcohol intake, and pregnancy. Many medications also are known to precipitate hypertriglyceridemia, including oral contraceptives, corticosteroids, tamoxifen, antihypertensives, isotretinoin, bile acid binding resins, cyclophosphamide, antiretroviral regimens, and psychotropic medications[07,09]

Our patient was on an oral contraceptive but had a previously abnormal lipid profile on this medication, so we do not believe it is the "second hit" that caused the clinical manifestation of her disease. Severe hypertriglyceridemia has been described with systemic lupus erythematosus. Some speculate that systemic inflammation may lead to disordered lipolysis and hypertriglyceridemia in SLE. Additionally, autoimmune hyperlipidemia has been described. We postulate that the same mechanism may have precipitated the hypertriglyceridemia in our patient. Alternatively, it may have been the combination of medications used to treat her pruritus that was the "second hit" that unmasked her type III hyperlipidemia [1,2,3]

We also believe our patient had an element of lipoprotein X (Lp-X). Her degree of hypercholesterolemia was out of proportion to the elevation of her Apo B level (Apo B level of 267 mg/dL with a simultaneous total cholesterol level of 1,765 mg/dL). In contrast to type III hyperlipidemia, Lp-X is usually not associated with premature coronary disease and some believe it may even have anti-oxidant LDL activity. Our patient had a positive coronary calcium score and it may have been the development of Lp-X that leads the coronary atherosclerosis usually seen with elevated Apo B levels. This case illustrates the complexities in the diagnosis and management of dual lipid disorders and the importance of the identification of a "second hit" in type III hyperlipidemia (Trinick et al, 2013).

CONCLUSION:

TVD (Tripplevessels disease) because of hyperlipidemia is extremely uncommon in young age. This study expects to give mindfulness about hyperlipidemia just as a refreshed information about the study of disease transmission and risk factor of hyperlipidemia. We also believe our patient had an element of lipoprotein X (Lp-X). In contrast to type III hyperlipidemia, Lp-X is usually not associated with premature coronary disease and some believe it may even have anti-oxidant LDL activity. Her degree of hypercholesterolemia was out of proportion to the elevation of her Apo B level (Apo B level of 267 mg/dL with a simultaneous total cholesterol level of 1,765 mg/dL). Hyperlipidemia Hyperlipidemia is a genetic disorder resulting in the accumulation of remnant particles stemming from a defective Apo E, resulting in an elevated cholesterol and triglyceride level. Common precipitants of hypertriglyceridemia include type 2 diabetes, hypothyroidism, renal failure, obesity, alcohol intake, and pregnancy. Some speculate that systemic inflammation may lead to disordered lipolysis and hypertriglyceridemia in SLE. Additionally, autoimmune hyperlipidemia has been described. We postulate that the same mechanism may have precipitated the hypertriglyceridemia in our patient. The disease is caused by defective forms of Apo E that ineffectively bind to lipoprotein receptors, leading to accumulation of chylomicron and VLDL remnants.[10,13]

Additional file:**Abbreviations:**

TVD (Tripplevessels disease), CHD (Chronic heart disease), (ASCVD) Atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease, SOB (Shortness of breath).

Availability of data and materials:

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Author's contributions:

Asif Raza Gill and Ms. Hajira Sarwar contributed equally to this work.

Ethics approval and consent to participate:

The patient relatives had already agreed and signed the consent form.

Competing interests:

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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